

PHOTOSYNTHESIS AND PHOTOELECTRIC CONVERTERS

Kasimjanova Hamidahon Botirjon qizi Andijan

State University, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics, 3rd year student of Physics

Rahmonkulova Nargiza Baxromjon qizi

Andijan State University, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics, 3rd year student of Physics

Abstract: *This article discusses the use of other forms of energy in addition to renewable energy sources in nature, through photosynthesis, which is currently being used by humans, and the production of energy from photoelectric converters. The process of formation of organic compounds from inorganic compounds using the energy of sunlight is also analyzed.*

Keywords: *renewable energy, photosynthesis, photoelectric converter, inorganic compound, electromagnetic radiation, photoeffect, semiconductors, biomass.*

Photosynthesis The word "photosynthesis" is derived from the Greek words "photos" - light, "synthesis" - compound words, and the process of forming organic matter from carbon dioxide - CO. The process of photosynthesis in plants is the basis of all life on Earth. Due to the process of photosynthesis: Plants use solar energy to produce organic compounds that serve as food for all living organisms except inorganic compounds. The air that surrounds the planet we breathe, as well as all the energy produced by the world's energy, is the energy of fossil fuels, the product of the photosynthesis of plants that once lived on Earth. 'lgandir. The total heat energy given off by photosynthesis in the world's forests is $40 \cdot 10^{12} \text{W}$ equivalent energy. This energy is 10 times more than the oil and gas energy currently mined [1]. Photosynthesis is the process of forming organic compounds from inorganic compounds using the energy of sunlight. Its biological significance is to provide living organisms on Earth with organic matter and to enrich the Earth's atmosphere with oxygen. Photosynthesis is a complex, multi-step process. Types of

photosynthesis include: 1) photosynthesis without chlorophyll; 2) chlorophyll photosynthesis: - anoxic; - oxygenated. Stages of photosynthesis: - photophysics; - chemical. In the first stage, the process of absorbing light quanta with pigments takes place, as a result of which they become excited and transmit their energy to other molecules in the photosystem. In the second stage, electrons split at the center of the reaction.

Electrons move along a chain that drives electrons. The two-stage process is called light-dependent photosynthesis. The third stage occurs in the absence of light and involves the reaction of biochemical synthesis of organic matter using the energy stored during light dependence. While humans and animals use oxygen to release carbon dioxide, carbon dioxide released into the atmosphere is the main source of carbon for plants. But plants absorb carbon dioxide only in light, and without light they also emit carbon dioxide. For example, a lot of houseplants and flowers growing in the room at night - a person who sleeps in this room in the dark consumes oxygen, which causes headaches due to lack of oxygen. In plants, photosynthesis takes place in chloroplasts. Chloroplasts can be found in the stem and fruit cells of plants, but the main organ of photosynthesis is the leaves of plants that are anatomically adapted to this process. This is because the leaves, which have a larger surface area, absorb most of the light for photosynthesis. Chlorophyll performs two different functions: absorbing sunlight, converting it into energy, and transmitting it. 90% of chlorophylls in chlorophyll groups belong to the group of light-collecting complexes. They act as antennas and transmit the stored energy to the reaction center of the photosystem. Today, biomass is an important energy source, as 10% of the energy used in the world comes from biomass. Biomass will continue to be the main source of energy in these countries. In developing countries, deforestation and deforestation are increasing the risk of deforestation in many countries. Substitute photoelectric converters are being developed for semiconductor devices that convert sunlight into electricity. The principle of operation of photoelectric transducers is based on the phenomenon of the photoelectric effect, which converts electromagnetic radiation (light energy) into electrical energy [4]. There are three

main types of photo effects. 1. External photoeffect - under the influence of radiation, electrons are released from the surface of the cathode metal into the vacuum surrounding it. 2. Internal photoeffect - a change in the electrical conductivity of semiconductors under the influence of light. The photoelectric effect of a closed layer of two semiconductors with different types of conductivity. In the conversion of electromagnetic radiation energy into electrical energy, in practice, the third photoeffect method is mainly used, which is called the r-p transition photoeffect. The following process takes place in the r-p transition photo effect. The p semiconductor has excess free electrons, and the r semiconductor has positive holes. As a result of their interaction, electron diffusion is observed. The diffusion continues until the relative and positive charge concentrations in the contact plane (closed layer) form a potential difference that equalizes the diffusion of charges. However, the potential difference generated in the interaction cannot be used, because in a closed chain it is equal to the difference in potentials with the same inverse sign. If light is applied to the contact plane, an additional pair of electron holes are formed in both semiconductors. Under the influence of their contact difference, the potential difference interferes: electrons pass through the p semiconductor and negatively charge it; the cracks pass to the r semiconductor and charge it positively. As the contact plane is constantly illuminated, an additional difference in potentials creates a constant electric current in the outer circuit. The r semiconductor is covered with a very thin, practically transparent p semiconductor to allow it to illuminate the contact surface. The set of solar elements that make up solar panels is prepared in the same way. Various semiconductors are currently being explored and tested around the world to create high-efficiency solar cells (low-cost and high-FIC). Today, there are examples of thin-film photocells based on three (and more) component semiconductor compounds. There have also been successes in using monocrystalline silicon elements, which are more expensive but more efficient than thin-film elements. In the future, it is possible to create solar cells with a FIC of more than 30% (the FIC of modern silicon photocells does not exceed 15%). Currently, various solar collecting systems are used to reduce the cost of the

converter and increase its overall efficiency. In this case, the polymer lens serves as a low-cost device that collects sunlight on a small area. This, in turn, will reduce the cost of the photocell and, consequently, the use of more expensive, high-efficiency solar cells. The use of point-focus Fresnel lenses for this purpose allows to collect several hundred times more sunlight than natural radiation, as well as to increase the efficiency of the main output parameters of the photocell accordingly. However, the use of solar radiation collection has a number of features that are not typical of photovoltaic systems without collectors. Also, during the absorption of the accumulated radiation, a large amount of heat is released from the solar cells, which needs to be effectively dissipated. In addition, the focused light spot must not extend beyond the boundaries of the element and ensure that the element is precisely positioned relative to the sun. To do this, you need to use a special system that monitors the movement of the sun. The use of light collectors leads to an increase in the output energy characteristics of the solar cell, including power and electricity generation in the evening (which is also very important for the operation of a solar power plant in the power system), as well as the energy efficiency of the device. the translator is his FIK. The energy of solar radiation can be converted into constant electricity. It uses thin silicon films and some other semiconductor material. Potential advantages of photovoltaic energy conversion: absence of moving parts; service life more than 100 years; simplicity of operation, the possibility of efficient use of solar radiation. However, this method of energy production is 75 times more expensive than conventional energy production [5].

Therefore, work is currently underway on devices that produce cheaper electricity. For example, arsenic is used instead of silicon. A photovoltaic generator, a solar cell, is a device that converts light energy into electrical energy. When light strikes a photocell, an electric current is generated in the photoelectric generator. The operation of the most efficient photovoltaic generator is based on the electromotive force (EMF) that is excited at the boundary between a conductor and a light-sensitive semiconductor (such as silicon) or a conductor of different sexes. The photoelectric generator is assembled in the form of a flat panel from individual

semiconductor photocells with a thickness of less than 0.2-0.3 mm. The power from a 1-2 m surface photovoltaic generator is 200-300 W, and the FIC is 10-20%. A photoelectric generator can generate up to a few kW • cm² of ultra-high intensity radiation energy. The advantages of a photovoltaic generator are its compactness, long service life, ease of use, and the fact that it does not emit harmful gases. Photoelectric generators are used in spacecraft, automatic weather stations, etc. [6].

Photocell - The ECG or electrical performance of light radiation is based on the phenomenon of photoelectric emission or internal photoeffect. A photoelectric vacuum based on photoelectric emission consists of two electrodes, a cathode and an anode electrovacuum, placed in a glass or tube filled with gas. The stream of light incident on the photocathode generates photoelectron emission on its surface. When a photovoltaic circuit is connected, a photocurrent current proportional to the luminous flux is generated. Photocathode sliding - sensory and oxygen - sensing photoelectrons are common. Photoelectrons usually serve as receivers of radiation or light. Semiconductor photoelectrons are used in solar cells and photovoltaic generators to convert solar energy directly into electricity.

List of used literature:

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